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Design and implementation of an active load test rig for high-precision evaluation of servomechanisms in industrial applications

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ABSTRACT

Position-controlled servomechanisms are the core elements of flexible manufacturing plants, primarily utilized to actuate robotic systems and automated machines. To match specific torque and costs requirements, typical servomechanism arrangements comprise precision reducers, which introduce motion errors that heavily limit the final performance achievable. Such errors are complex to model and depend from speed, dynamic loading conditions and temperature. Accurate characterization is fundamental to develop digital twins and advanced control strategies aimed at their active prediction and compensation. To properly assess the servomechanisms behavior and elaborate high-fidelity virtual models, instrumented test rigs have been proposed which can replicate the time-varying working conditions encountered in real industrial environments. In this context, the present paper reports about a novel engineering method for developing an active loading apparatus, namely a programmable mechatronic device that can deliver custom loads in a highly dynamic manner. The proposed system, consisting of a secondary servomotor and related rotating vector reducer, is integrated and synchronized within an existing instrumented test rig and is controlled in torque mode via a programmable logic controller. The paper mainly focuses on the description of the implemented closed-loop control and on the related tuning and calibration processes, demonstrating that the proposed solutions avoid important measurement errors that could compromise the final effectiveness of the system. The study finally explores the potential benefits of introducing a filter to further enhance system performance. At last, to prove the importance of stabilizing the rig and demonstrate the influence of the control parameters on its measurements, a standard test aimed at assessing the reducer transmission error is conducted adopting different parameter settings.

1. Introduction

The Industry 4.0 has significantly transformed production processes, which are now characterized by heightened levels of automation, enhancing flexibility and enabling a superior degree of customization [1–3]. In this context, Industrial Robots (IR) are becoming core elements in many automated plants as they can perform multiple tasks and support different types of tools [4].

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in empowering IR to execute manufacturing operations that require accuracy and productivity traditionally achieved with computer numerical control machines [5–7]. Compared to these machines, which are specifically designed for operations demanding high forces and very accurate tool motion, IR possess several advantages, including increased Degrees of Freedom (DoF) and dexterity that allow working with more complex geometries, greater flexibility and lower life-cycle costs [2,8–12]. Nevertheless, according to Refs. [13–15], achieving precise control over the

position, orientation, and force of the tool connected to the end-effector of an IR requires the compensation of the main kinematic and dynamic errors, which still prevent the IR from being adopted in high-precision tasks.

As discussed in Ref. [1], such errors can be divided into two main groups, namely controller and components errors. The former are strictly related to the control laws implemented in the commercial IR controllers [16], whereas the latter directly refer to the errors that exist in the IR mechanics (i.e. links and joints). The links, for example, may present geometric errors and also deform due to changes in the environment temperature over a long working period [5,17], causing notable positioning errors at the end-effector. However, the majority of the mechanical errors are produced by the servomechanisms embedded in the IR joints [18,19]. For medium-to-high payload IR, these modules are composed of a servomotor and a high-ratio speed reducer, in

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Fig. 1. Assessment of joint errors in IR via external sensors.

which transmission defects are primarily observed, as documented in Refs. [11,20–22].

According to Ref. [18], the most commonly used option, named Rotate Vector (RV) reducer, is a two-stage solution consisting of a planetary gear followed by a cycloid-pin gear. Although optimized in terms of size and torque capacity (and even sold as a “zero backlash” solution), such reducer type is affected by an unavoidable backlash (usually around 1 arcmin) and torsional compliance, which negatively impact the IR motion performance. In particular, the backlash reduces the final resolution and accuracy, especially during initial movements and inversion of motions, as the small movements made by the servomotor are not transmitted to the output side of the reducer (i.e. the robot link) but rather recover the clearance between the teeth of two gears, generating a Transmission Error (TE) and a Lost Motion (LM) [1,23]. As said, reducers are also characterized by low mechanical stiffness [8,9], which reduces the natural frequency of the entire robot mechanism, also limiting the bandwidth for correction when implementing closed-loop control strategies [5]. As demonstrated in previous researches [19,24], the reducer’s TE and LM change depending on the specific operated conditions (speed, load, oil temperature, state-of-degradation, etc.), that is why in-depth experimental analyses are needed to correctly capture and map the reducer nonlinear behavior and develop innovative compensation strategies.

To evaluate the TE for each reducer, one could perform measurements on the robot and compare the signals acquired at the input and output shafts via the servomotor-embedded encoder and an external position sensor (e.g. a secondary encoder [25] or a laser tracker [26]) respectively, as schematized in Fig. 1. Despite its practical simplicity, this setup has several limitations, namely: (i) poor measurement quality, mainly due to the rather limited resolution, accuracy and sampling time of the servomotor encoders; (ii) inability to measure a complete joint revolution; (iii) lack of accurate info regarding the temperature and the load acting on the specific joint during the test; (iv) purchase and installation costs (e.g. more than 70k€ in the case of a laser tracker).

1.1. Problem statement

To overcome these limitations and ensure high-quality assessments of the reducer transmission performance (e.g. evaluating TE and LM), a commonly employed strategy in the literature involves the use of specialized test rigs. These mechatronic systems (different architectures are discussed in Ref. [27]) enable the testing of robotic servomechanisms under diverse operating conditions using an open, programmable controller and a sophisticated sensory apparatus. Generally, they also include a loading system designed to apply resistant torque to the reducer’s output shaft. In the simplest configuration, this may be represented by a gravity–torque conversion mechanism [28,29], which

becomes useful to deliver static loads but cannot be employed to run dynamic tests with custom time-varying torque profiles. Other researches have utilized a magnetic brake to reach higher torque levels (see Refs. [30,31]), although also in this case custom high-dynamic loads cannot be imposed.

A viable alternative is to install a secondary motor (either a servomotor or a torque motor) at the reducer’s output shaft, as illustrated in Refs. [32,33]. Proper motor sizing is crucial in both scenarios, as the torque required at the reducer’s output is significantly greater than that applied by the primary, position-controlled, servomotor at the input shaft. Given that RV reducers can have extremely high reduction ratios (up to 270 in the initial joints of many heavy-duty IR) [34], using torque motors might not always be practical due to their large size. Therefore, an increasingly preferred solution is to combine the secondary servomotor with a reducer, as this configuration allows to meet the required torque levels but also to maintain high-dynamic capabilities while reducing both the rig’s radial size and costs [35,36].

Despite the referenced works have offered valuable insights into the principles and procedures for RV reducers testing, there are still several open issues concerning the rig calibration, control and tuning operations when these active loading systems (i.e. the combined use of a secondary servomotor and reducer) are utilized. One significant aspect is the impact of newly installed components, such as the secondary servomechanism and its related hardware and software interfaces, on the rig mechatronic systems, which remains an open question requiring further investigation. The loading system and its controller influence to the overall dynamic behavior of the rig, introducing new disturbances, shifting resonance frequencies, and affecting stability during testing. Addressing these challenges is essential before commencing the experimental campaign to ensure optimal measurement quality and accurate data extrapolation.

1.2. Contributions and paper structure

Building on the previous considerations and with the intent to address the identified gaps, the present paper offers the following novel contributions:

1. Engineering methods and tools to optimize the dynamic operation and measurement quality of test rigs implementing an active loading apparatus. The proposed model-based approach combines theoretical and practical knowledge, supported by extensive experimental activities on the rig, and involves the calculation and simulation of Transfer Functions (TF).
2. An integrated framework for the efficient design and implementation of the active load, facilitating the prediction of its response and the tuning of key parameters under varying inputs and working conditions.
3. Practical guidelines to streamline the reported procedures and support their reproduction with other similar system.
4. An open-source dataset from the experiments and predictive models, provided to support further developments.

The research is carried out by taking into consideration the test rig described in Ref. [22] and partially prototyped in Ref. [24]. The successful completion of the full prototype represents a valuable contribution to the field, providing a tangible example of the application and feasibility of the proposed design in practical settings. After an exhaustive description of the experimental setup, focused on identifying the main modules of the rig and explaining their mechanical and electronic connections during operation, the paper delves into the definition of a mechatronic model by combining analytical and experimental methods. The findings from this research contribute to the understanding and improvement of the active load performance, allowing for more effective and optimized operation of the test rig in various scenarios.

The rest of the present paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 describes the experimental equipment and outlines the adopted approach.

Fig. 2. Overview of the test rig equipment and layout.

Section 3 focuses on the rig mechanical modeling and dynamic identification. Section 4 is dedicated to the design and implementation of the active loading system. In Section 5, a series of experiments is presented to validate the proposed approach. Additionally, a strategy involving the implementation of a filter is proposed to enhance the rig overall performance. Finally, the conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

2. Experimental equipment and methodology

In this section, a description of the employed test rig is given by covering different aspects related to its mechanical architecture, hardware components, and acquisition system. Emphasis is placed on detailing the functional modules that contribute to the rig's performance [34]. For a more comprehensive understanding of the design considerations made behind this prototype, the interested reader may refer to Ref. [22]. In the last part of the section, an overview of the proposed approach for the design and implementation of an active loading system is provided, which will guide the reader through the subsequent technical sections.

2.1. Test rig description

The overall test rig structure is depicted in Fig. 2, where the main hardware components are identified (see also Table 1 for details). Compared to the setup discussed in [24], the new rig configuration consists of two servomechanisms connected by a central shaft. The first servomechanism (formed by a Bosch servomotor and a Nabtesco RV 160N reducer with a reduction ratio of 81) represents the system under test, whereas the second one (formed by a Bosch servomotor and a similar reducer but featuring a reduction ratio of 156) serves as the active loading system. This apparatus, used to apply customized time-varying torque profiles on the tested servomechanism, is the focus of the current investigation.

The servomotors are directly controlled by their Bosch drives and managed at higher level with a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) by Beckhoff. The PLC facilitates the synchronous communication with the drives, which are responsible for controlling the power delivered to the servomotors, and with the installed sensory apparatus, as shown

in Fig. 2. An EtherCAT fieldbus is utilized to establish such communication at a rate of 4000 Hz (i.e. PLC task cycle time of 0.25 ms). The EtherCAT protocol employs a master-slave communication model, where the PLC serves as the master and the I/O devices function as slaves. At each cycle, the exchanged process data is contained within an EtherCAT frame, which passes through all the slaves sequentially. The correct signal synchronization is allowed by the so-called Distributed Clock function, which will be detailed in Section 2.2.

For the correct and effective utilization of the proposed rig device, the following sub-systems must be identified and thoroughly analyzed:

- **Motor Side (MS):** it represents the mechanical transmission at the input side of the tested reducer. Unlike the servomechanisms commonly mounted on robots, where the reducer is directly connected to the servomotor shaft, additional mechanical components are installed here to enable sensorization of the transmission. These include a multi-plate coupling, an angular encoder and a strain gauge torquemeter. Other signals are sampled inside the servomotor, which provides feedback on the actual position, recorded through its integrated encoder, along with the absorbed current (to be transformed in torque data by considering the servomotor torque constant).
- **Load Side (LS):** similar to the MS, it corresponds to the mechanical transmission at the input side of the secondary reducer. In this portion of the rig, the only measurable quantities are provided by the servomotor.
- **Slow Shaft (SS):** it serves as the central shaft connecting the output side of the reducers. It includes another set of sensors (encoder and torquemeter), a multi-plate coupling and a series of flanges and mechanical interfaces.

By acquiring signals from the abovementioned sensors placed respectively at the MS and SS, the reducer dynamic TE, LM and efficiency can be directly computed during the rig functioning. Then, to take into account the effect of the oil temperature variations, which cause alterations in the reducer's dynamic behavior, a temperature sensor is inserted in the reducer cases, as visible in Fig. 2.

As notable from Table 1, several components of the rig have measurement limits concerning speed and torque, which must be respected

Table 1
Characteristics of the installed commercial components.

Side	Component	Description	Rated/Max speed	Rated/Max torque
Motor Side (MS)	Servomotor	Bosch MS2N7-DOBHN	2000/4000 rpm	22/73.2 Nm
	Encoder	Renishaw Ring: RESA 100 mm Renishaw Readhead: RESOLUTE	-/19000 rpm	-/-
	Torquemeter	Manner measuring flange	-/8000 rpm	50/200 Nm
	Reducer	Nabtesco RV-160N (red. ratio $\tau_{MS} = 81$)	15/48 rpm (output)	1600/8000 Nm (output)
	Thermoresistance	Industrie technik STIC-PT1000/135	-/-	-/-
	Shaft coupling	Mayr ROBA-DS size 25	-/11800 rpm	290/435 Nm
Slow Shaft (SS)	Encoder	Renishaw Ring: RESA 200 mm Renishaw Readhead: RESOLUTE	-/9500 rpm	-/-
	Torquemeter	Manner measuring flange	-/9500 rpm	2000/8000 Nm
	Shaft coupling	Mayr ROBA-DS size 300	-/6200 rpm	3500/5250 Nm
Load Side (LS)	Reducer	Nabtesco RV-160N (red. ratio $\tau_{LS} = 156$)	15/48 rpm (output)	1600/8000 Nm (output)
	Thermoresistance	Industrie technik STIC-PT1000/135	-/-	-/-
	Servomotor	Bosch MS2N7-COBHN	2000/4000 rpm	27.2/70.5 Nm
	Shaft coupling	Mayr ROBA-DS size 40	-/10100 rpm	450/675 Nm

Fig. 3. Torque signal time diagram and delays calculation within the PLC-based control framework.

to prevent damages. In particular, the system is limited in torque by the sensors which can support a torque lower than the maximum value that the servomotors can apply. In this work, it is deemed appropriate not to exceed the torquemeters measuring limit values and, consequently, a maximum torque value of 50 Nm and of 2000 Nm is established for the MS and the SS. Additionally, it has been decided to operate at a speed below the maximum working speed of the servomotors. By taking into account the limits of the secondary servomotor (4000 rpm) and the reduction ratio of both reducers ($\tau_{MS} = 81$ and $\tau_{LS} = 156$), the maximum speed at MS was set equal to 1800 rpm, which corresponds to 3467 rpm at the LS. Any additional limitation that characterizes the system must be verified experimentally. For instance, conducting simple tests at constant speed imposed by the servomotor at the MS reveals an important effect on the rig's operability, depending on the state of the servomotor at the LS. Specifically, if the LS servomotor is disabled, the maximum achievable speed before reaching torque levels close to 2000 Nm at the SS is 1600 rpm. This is attributed to the interaction between the permanent magnets and the windings present on the stator of the disabled LS servomotor, generating a braking torque effect. To ensure the rig's working range remains uncompromised, it is required to enable the LS servomotor and impose a null torque set-point during testing. This will prevent the undesirable braking torque and allow for a more expansive and reliable operating range.

2.2. Signals time mapping

As previously mentioned, this work leverages the Distributed Clock function provided by EtherCAT technology to synchronize the I/O data.

The primary goal is to establish precise and deterministic correlation among signals, enabling the design of a stable and robust closed-loop torque controller for the active loading system. The time diagram of the torque signals managed at the PLC level is depicted in Fig. 3, where both the feedback torque sampled by the torquemeter at the SS and the torque commanded to the servomotor at the LS are defined in the context of a single PLC cycle. The functional schematic of the active loading system and detailed descriptions about its practical implementation and tuning will be given in the next sections. In this context, two key parameters are defined when designing the PLC controller: the Input Shift, indicating how old the sampled torque feedback is, and the Output Shift, indicating when the newly calculated torque command will take effect in the drive. These parameters facilitate the calculation of the maximum controller bandwidth. After computations, the determined time interval (Δt_{tot} in Fig. 3) is approximately 829.78 µs, which corresponds to a maximum correction frequency of 1205 Hz.

2.3. Active loading system design method

The design and implementation of an active loading system within the previously discussed setup present several challenges. The test rig must replicate a variety of operating conditions encountered by the tested servomechanisms in real machines and robots (see Ref. [19] for details). Therefore, on one hand, the loading system must function stably across a wide operating range to maintain high measurement performance in each scenario. On the other hand, it should be as simple as possible, allowing for quick setup and tuning without requiring in-depth knowledge from the operator. According to industry standards

Fig. 4. Active load design workflow.

in automation, a suitable solution could be a PID torque controller, whose tuning is typically addressed through a limited set of parameters (gains). However, as is well known, these gains are rarely optimal across all machine operating conditions. A parameter set that works well in one situation may not deliver the same control performance in another. A major concern, therefore, is finding a parameter set that avoids unstable dynamic behavior, thereby ensuring the stability of the test rig during experimentation. Rig stability is crucial in this type of setup, which is widely used in the literature for the performance assessment of industrial reducers [27]. PID controllers are typically tuned using experimental approaches, such as the Ziegler–Nichols method or other well-documented techniques [37]. While these methods provide a quick way to set up and commission new machines for specific operating conditions, they become impractical when the machine must operate under varying conditions.

To enable rapid and efficient computation of the PID parameters, facilitating the adaptation of the loading system and ensuring stable rig operation, in this work a model-based approach is proposed and implemented. As illustrated in Fig. 4, this approach involves several sequential steps aimed at developing an accurate and computationally efficient mechatronic model of the test rig. First, the rig's mechanical unit is analytically modeled to derive its TF (denoted as TF_{Mech}). This model is then verified and refined using experimental data collected during dedicated tests to obtain the final TF ($TF_{Mech,est}$). Next, the overall rig TF ($TF_{Test\ rig}$) is constructed by incorporating the contributions from the PID controller (TF_{PID}) and the filter (TF_{Filt}), and subsequently implemented in the Matlab environment to perform stability analysis. The obtained tool allows for the rapid computation of Root Locus (RL) and the assessment of controller performance, enabling quick evaluation and adaptation of the loading system for any test condition. Detailed explanations of each step will be provided in the following sections. To ease the reproduction of the proposed method, a folder containing the utilized scripts is shared from the supplementary material section.

3. Test rig mechanical modeling

This section focuses on the test rig mechanical modeling and reports a simplified yet effective analytical formulation for the estimation of the mechanical TF, which will play a crucial role in the subsequent section, i.e. when dealing with the implementation and tuning of the active torque controller. Such approach is fundamental also for the development of digital twins of automated machines and robotic manipulators, since it allows a fast computing of the behavior of the physical assets in its corresponding digital replica. Throughout this discussion, a combined approach incorporating both theoretical and experimental methods is followed to ensure a comprehensive analysis.

3.1. Theoretical model

According to Refs. [24,38,39], to ensure the rig dynamic stability and avoid potential issues during measurements, the dynamic behavior of the purely mechanical system must be first assessed. For this purpose,

the entire test rig has been discretized into a lumped-parameter 4 DoFs torsional dynamic model consisting of four disks as follows: MS servomotor, tested reducer, second reducer, and LS servomotor, along with three torsional springs with linear elastic behavior and three dampers, as shown in Fig. 5. The model can be further refined by considering that during the rig functioning the MS servomotor imposes a pre-defined motion to the first disk (j_1), which is then constrained in position. The number of DoFs to be analyzed can therefore be reduced to 3. On the other side, the LS servomotor acts as an external torque generator on the last disk (j_4). According to these considerations, the dynamic equation of motion after applying the Laplace transform can be expressed as follows:

$$(\mathbf{J}s^2 + \mathbf{C}s + \mathbf{K})\boldsymbol{\theta} = \mathbf{M} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{J} , \mathbf{C} , and \mathbf{K} are the inertial, damping, and stiffness matrices respectively, the vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ represents the DoFs of the inertial components and the vector \mathbf{M} contains the external torques acting on the disks. These matrices and vectors have the following form:

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{bmatrix} j_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & j_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & j_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 + c_2 & -c_2 & 0 \\ -c_2 & c_2 + c_3 & -c_3 \\ 0 & -c_3 & c_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} k_1 + k_2 & -k_2 & 0 \\ -k_2 & k_2 + k_3 & -k_3 \\ 0 & -k_3 & k_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\theta} = \begin{pmatrix} \theta_2 \\ \theta_3 \\ \theta_4 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ M_4 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

being j_2, j_3, j_4 the inertial parameters, c_1, c_2, c_3 the damping parameters and k_1, k_2, k_3 the mechanical stiffness parameters.

The theoretical TF between the input, which corresponds to the excitation torque imposed by the LS servomotor (i.e. M_4) and the output, which corresponds to the torque measured by the torque meter installed on the SS (defined as $(k_2 + c_2s)(\theta_3 - \theta_2)$ from Fig. 5) becomes:

$$TF_{Mech}(s) = \frac{(k_2 + c_2s)(\theta_3 - \theta_2)}{M_4} \quad (7)$$

After inverting Eq. (1) and solving for $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, Eq. (7) can be rewritten as:

$$TF_{Mech}(s) = \frac{k_2 + c_2s}{\det(\mathbf{J}s^2 + \mathbf{C}s + \mathbf{K})} [J_2c_3s^3 + (J_2k_3 + c_1c_2)s^2 + (k_3c_1 + k_1c_3)s + k_2k_1] \quad (8)$$

The natural frequencies and mode shapes of the mechanical system are determined by solving the denominator of Eq. (8). Prior to this, the lumped parameters must be determined, either based on the data reported on the components datasheets or by performing simple

Fig. 5. Test rig functioning: (a) adopted PLC-based schematic for servomotor control; (b) lumped parameters mechanical model of the transmission.

Table 2

Inertia and stiffness parameters of mechanical components (obtained elaborating data from datasheets).

Element	Value	Unit
Inertia		
J_2	16.7	kgm ²
J_3	92.1	kgm ²
J_4	169.8	kgm ²
Stiffness		
k_1	6.12×10^7	Nm/rad
k_2	3.64×10^5	Nm/rad
k_3	1.12×10^9	Nm/rad
Damping		
$c_{1,2,3}$	0.01	Nms/rad

evaluation resorting to Computer-Aided Design and Engineering tools. Considering the presence of three different shaft speeds in the rig, the parameters must be converted to their corresponding parameters on the SS exploiting the energy equivalence principle. By adopting the values listed in Table 2, the resulting vector of natural frequencies becomes:

$$f_{nat} = \begin{pmatrix} 5.94 \\ 305.96 \\ 694.23 \end{pmatrix} \text{ Hz}$$

Based on the conducted modal analysis, the primary effect of the first natural frequency (5.94 Hz) is on the J_4 disk, i.e. the LS shaft.

3.2. Transfer function estimation

Due to uncertainties in the lumped parameters, especially the damping coefficients, the TF_{Mech} obtained from Eq. (8) has been utilized as

a reference to determine the degrees of the numerator and denominator polynomials (4 and 6, respectively) for the experimental estimation of the TF, denoted as $TF_{Mech,est}$. During the test, a sine sweep with an amplitude of 0.2 Nm was applied to the rig using the LS servomotor, covering a frequency range from 0 to 30 Hz. The MS servomotor was used to rotate the system at a constant speed, with the LS servomotor being enabled once the target speed was reached. For experiments conducted at speeds greater than 1500 rpm, the LS servomotor was enabled at the beginning of the experiment due to the limitations described in Section 2.1. The measurements have been carried out at $\omega_{MS} = \{100, 500, 1000, 1400, 1800\}$ rpm. During the experiments, speed fluctuations at the MS were minimized as much as possible by finely tuning the Bosch drive system and employing an effective torque ripple compensation strategy, as previously proposed by the Authors in Ref. [24]. As a result, the maximum speed deviation from the nominal value was $\{2.41, 0.49, 0.31, 0.20, 0.19\}$ % for the five tested speeds respectively.

To obtain the $TF_{Mech,est}$, the recorded signals, namely the input torque applied by the LS servomotor and the output torque acquired by the SS torquemeter, have been processed using the `tfest` algorithm of the Matlab library. As outlined above, in line with the theoretical modeling (see Eq. (8)), during this estimation process the degree of the numerator and denominator polynomial was set equal to 4 and 6 in Matlab. To validate the use of the linear TF in describing the dynamic behavior of the rig in the analyzed frequency range, the coherence parameter was employed, as documented in Refs. [40,41]. This parameter assigns a value between 0 and 1, indicating the degree of linear correlation between the two acquired torque signals. Fig. 6 compares the coherence plot over frequency for the five analyzed experiments. In all cases, it can be observed that the parameter is very low for frequencies below 2 Hz and then starts to increase. Moreover,

Fig. 6. Evaluation of coherence parameter for the five performed experiments.

Table 3

First natural frequency and average coherence obtained from the $TF_{Mech,est}$ evaluated with the five performed experiments.

ω_{MS} [rpm]	f_{nat} [Hz]	Avg. Coherence
100	5.16	0.77
500	5.25	0.81
1000	5.36	0.83
1400	5.38	0.83
1800	5.36	0.80

for the speed of 100 rpm, the coherence value is lower compared to the speeds of 500, 1000, 1400, and 1800 rpm. This may be due to the Stribeck effect studied in detail in Refs. [24,42], where the nonlinear behavior of the internal reducer friction has been modeled as a function of the input speed (ω_{MS}). In particular, this curve shows that, for speeds lower than about 300 rpm, the friction is not purely viscous but rather mixed, due to the presence of both viscous and rolling friction caused by the roughness of the reducer components. Consequently, the system does not exhibit linear behavior. However, for speeds above 500 rpm, the viscous friction is largely predominant and a quasi-linear behavior can be expected. Additionally, the poorer TF estimation at 100 rpm may be due to the greater speed fluctuations. To evaluate the experiment that best approximated the system using a linear model, the average coherence in the analyzed frequency range was considered, as reported in Table 3. Given that the experimental data utilized to derive $TF_{Mech,est}$ is confined to frequencies up to 30 Hz, its application has been constrained to this range. In addition, Table 3 presents the first natural frequency of the mechanical system, identified from various versions of the $TF_{Mech,est}$, each generated using a single vector of experimental data corresponding to one of the five different speeds. Such frequency spans from 5.16 Hz to 5.36 Hz, averaging at 5.30 Hz with a 10% deviation from the theoretical result obtained in Section 3.1. At last, by examining the Bode plot in Fig. 7, it can be seen that the mechanical system's response to the torque input generated by the LS servomotor exhibits characteristics of a low-pass filter. The frequency at which the amplitude is dampened by around -3 dB, representing the system's bandwidth, can be visualized. This frequency is estimated to be around 8.5 Hz.

4. Active loading system implementation

This section details the design and implementation of the active loading system operating on the analyzed mechanical system. The objective is to actively impose and regulate the torque on the SS during the servomechanism testing, as shown in Fig. 5. To achieve this, a PID controller has been adopted (see the schematic in Fig. 8) as an industrial standard with proven track records in automation, characterized by a simple design and high versatility [37,43,44]. This

Fig. 7. Bode plot of $TF_{Mech,est}$ evaluated with the five performed experiments.

was implemented in the TwinCAT software running on the PLC via a function block named FB_CTRL_PID from the Controller Toolbox library [45]. The key user-defined parameters within the block include the proportional gain (K_p), the integration time constant (T_i), the derivative time constant (T_v) and the low-pass filter time constant present in the derivative action (T_d). Additionally, the function block allows the selection of the controller action time, which was set to the PLC cycle time in this case (i.e. 250 μ s). As a feedback control loop, the block's input is the torque error, calculated as the difference between the torque measured by the torquemeter on the SS and the reference torque value, whereas the output, scaled by the reduction ratio of the second reducer (τ_{LS}) and then filtered, becomes the torque set-point to be assigned to the LS servomotor.

4.1. Mechatronic modeling

With reference to the schematic in Fig. 8, the implementation of a stable and predictable PID controller builds upon the understanding of both the dynamic behavior of the mechanical system and the attributes of the control and filtering modules in use. The former is effectively encapsulated within $TF_{Mech,est}$ (detailed in Section 3.2), whereas the latter is to be defined in this phase. Specifically, the TF of the implemented PID module, extracted from the TwinCAT manual, is as follows:

$$TF_{PID}(s) = K_p \left(1 + \frac{1}{T_i s} + \frac{T_v s}{1 + T_d s} \right) = K_p \tilde{TF}_{PID} \quad (9)$$

Now, by simply indicating as TF_{Filt} the TF of a generic filter module (whose effect will be analyzed in Section 5), with reference to the schematic in Fig. 8, the global TF of the rig mechatronic system, denoted as $TF_{Test rig}$, which relates the reference torque to the torque measured on the SS within a standard closed-loop controller, can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} TF_{Test rig}(s) &= \frac{TF_{PID} TF_{Filt} TF_{Mech,est}}{1 + TF_{PID} TF_{Filt} TF_{Mech,est}} \\ &= \frac{K_p \tilde{TF}_{PID} TF_{Filt} TF_{Mech,est}}{1 + K_p \tilde{TF}_{PID} TF_{Filt} TF_{Mech,est}} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

From a quick comparison of Eqs. (8) and (10), many changes can be observed when the closed-loop controller is enabled [46]. In particular, the presence of both control and filter parameters in the denominator polynomial shift the system's pole locations, consequently inducing changes in the natural frequencies. To prove this effect, simple tests were conducted without any filter by fixing the control parameters T_i , T_v and T_d as in Table 4 and adopting three different values of K_p , i.e. 0.5, 1 and 1.5. During the experiments, the system was rotated at a constant speed ($\omega_{MS} = 1400$ rpm) via the MS servomotor while a sine sweep torque was imposed as the reference to the controlled variable, namely the torque at the SS.

Fig. 8. Control schematic of the active loading system.

Parameter	Value [ms]
T_i	100
T_v	150
T_d	20

Fig. 9. Influence of K_p on the resonance frequency of the mechatronic system: (a) Torque recorded over time by the SS torquemeter (subtracted by its mean value); (b) Frequency spectrum.

Fig. 10. Simulated influence of three different K_p on the test rig resonance.

The results reported in Fig. 9 and in Table 5 show that as K_p increases, the resonance frequency shifts towards higher frequencies, stepping from 11.5 Hz to 19.7 Hz. In the case of $K_p = 0.5$, the resonance at 11.5 Hz could have been excited by the torque contribution from the pins inside the reducer (see Refs. [15,24] for detailed spectral analyses), which coincides with this frequency at the given speed, as shown by the following relation:

$$f_{pin} = \frac{\omega_{MS}}{60\tau_{MS}} n_{pin} = 11.5 \text{ Hz}$$

where $\omega_{MS}=1400$ rpm, $\tau_{MS} = 81$ and $n_{pin} = 40$ represent the imposed rotational speed, the reduction ratio, and the number of pins in the RV reducer, respectively. The same peaks are also present in the other two analyzed cases (i.e. when $K_p = 1$ or $K_p = 1.5$), although with smaller amplitudes as they do not coincide with the rig natural frequency. Al last, in Fig. 10 the amplitudes of the $TF_{Test\ rig}$ for the three different K_p values are shown. In this case, $TF_{Test\ rig}$ was obtained using the $TF_{Mech,est}$ evaluated in Section 3.2 from the experiment conducted at $\omega_{MS} = 1400$ rpm (highest average coherence, see Table 3). Overall, the tests confirmed that the term with the greatest impact on system stability is K_p , as it multiplies the other coefficients according to Eq. (9).

Overall, analyzing $TF_{Test\ rig}$, and specifically its natural frequencies which vary with the adopted control parameters, clearly highlights the importance of thoroughly evaluating and processing the input (reference) torque profile (derived from IR or machines) before initiating any performance assessment on the rig. In particular, it may be essential to filter out potential sources of excitation, which would otherwise compromise the measuring quality or potentially damage the rig system.

4.2. Stability analysis

After completing the modeling and dynamic identification of the test rig system, the next step in the stabilization process involves tuning the PID controller. According to Refs. [37,43,47,48], in this phase a valuable tool is the RL analysis, which provides significant insights and a visual representation of the system's response in relation to K_p . In this context, the values of T_i , T_v , and T_d have been fixed as done in Section 4.1 (values in Table 4).

The RL plot presented in Fig. 11 for $TF_{Test\ rig}$, generated using the Matlab function `rlocusplot`, depicts the system's behavior in relation to the K_p through various branches. By selecting a point on a branch, one can examine the corresponding K_p , poles, and damping of the system at that location. Consequently, it becomes possible to identify the critical K_p value at which the system becomes unstable and determine the associated diverging frequency. The RL plot highlights two distinct zones, as seen in Fig. 11. The white area denotes the instability for positive real values, whereas green area indicates stability

Table 5

Experimental resonance frequency Vs. estimated natural frequency of the test rig system (values expressed in Hz).

K_p	Experimental f_{res}	f_{nat} calculated from $TF_{Test\ rig}$ adopting:				
		$TF_{Mech,est}(100)$	$TF_{Mech,est}(500)$	$TF_{Mech,est}(1000)$	$TF_{Mech,est}(1400)$	$TF_{Mech,est}(1800)$
0.5	11.5	10.5	11.4	11.7	11.7	12.7
1	15.9	14.6	15.9	16.3	16.3	16.3
1.5	19.7	17.7	19.4	19.8	19.7	19.8

Fig. 11. RL of $TF_{Test\ rig}$ considering $TF_{Mech,est}$ obtained with experimental data collected at two different speeds: $\omega_{MS} = 1000$ rpm Vs. $\omega_{MS} = 1400$ rpm.

for negative real values. Consequently, it facilitates the identification of K_p that causes the system to traverse the imaginary axis, thereby establishing the maximum allowable K_p value for system stability.

It is important to note that Fig. 11 serves merely as an indicator to discern the instability of the system, being $TF_{Test\ rig}$ based on the estimated quantity $TF_{Mech,est}$. Therefore, the plot provides an approximation rather than an exact result, and there may be variations among the plots generated adopting different instances of $TF_{Mech,est}$ derived from experiments conducted at various speeds, such as $\omega_{MS} = 1000$ or 1400 rpm, as also noticeable from the results in Table 3. In the first case, the system exhibits resonance for $K_p > 2.06$, whereas in the second case this threshold becomes 1.66. These findings highlight the sensitivity of the system's stability and resonance characteristics to variations in the experimental conditions and underline the importance of selecting an appropriate K_p values for ensuring stability in mechatronic systems. Based on the analysis presented in Section 3.2, in the following sections all the validations will consider the $TF_{Mech,est}$ estimated from data collected at 1400 rpm.

4.3. Preliminary tests on physical prototype

To validate the described method and experimentally confirm the maximum K_p value, a series of preliminary tests were conducted. These consisted of the following sequential steps:

1. Run the MS servomotor until the user-defined speed is reached.
2. Enable torque control on LS by imposing a ramp to reach the required torque level on SS.
3. Record data points.
4. Gradually reduce the torque to zero using a new ramp, preventing any elastic rebound when removing the control defined by the PID. A new dataset is recorded around 0 Nm.
5. Decelerate the MS servomotor until it reaches 0rpm. At the same time, slow the SS torque at zero using the PID controller, ensuring that the system goes to a stop without any residual load on SS.

Fig. 12. Comparison between the experiments conducted with the controller parameters in Table 4 and $K_p = 1.4$ Vs. $K_p = 2$: (a) Torque recorded over time by the SS torquemeter; (b) Frequency spectrum.

In Fig. 12, the results of experiments conducted with two different K_p values are reported and compared. As noticeable, when $K_p = 2$, the system falls within the unstable zone of the RL graph (see Fig. 11, curve labeled 1400 rpm) and the torque recorded by the SS torquemeter starts to oscillate or even diverge, necessitating the termination of the experiment as a precautionary measure, as evident from Fig. 12(a). Conversely, for $K_p = 1.4$, the system remains in a stable state, as correctly predicted by the RL in Fig. 11, which indicates $K_p = 1.66$ as the threshold.

During this phase, additional experiments were conducted at various speeds, specifically at $\omega_{MS} = \{300, 700, 1300, 1500\}$ rpm by enforcing a constant torque $M_{ref} = -600$ Nm. Each experiment followed the same protocol, with various PID parameters being tested for each speed, as reported in Table 6. The RL is rapidly generated for each new scenario by simply updating the $TF_{Test\ rig}$ (specifically, TF_{PID}) with the new values of T_i , T_v and T_d . The outcomes of these tests, shown in Fig. 13, confirm the validity of the method.

Table 6
RL validation results.

ω_{MS} [rpm]	K_p Instable	K_p limit (from RL)	K_p stable	T_i [ms]	T_v [ms]	T_d [ms]
300	4.2	4.02	3.6	120	60	10
700	4	3.6	3.1	100	70	10
1300	2.5	2.2	2.1	200	100	20
1500	2.4	2	1.9	200	110	20

Fig. 13. Experiments to validate the controller stability method at different PID parameters and speeds using $TF_{Mech,est}$ previously obtained at $\omega_{MS} = 1400$ rpm: (a) $\omega_{MS} = 300$ rpm $M_{ref} = -600$ Nm; (b) $\omega_{MS} = 700$ rpm $M_{ref} = -600$ Nm; (c) $\omega_{MS} = 1300$ rpm $M_{ref} = -600$ Nm; (d) $\omega_{MS} = 1500$ rpm $M_{ref} = -600$ Nm. The main parameters of each tested condition are summarized in Table 6.

5. Performance validation

5.1. Improving system stability using a filter

With the aim of further stabilizing the system, the possibility of incorporating a filter to eliminate any possible excitation of the first natural frequency was explored. As previously discussed, the addition of the PID controller caused the poles associated with the purely mechanical system (i.e. $TF_{Mech,est}$) to shift according to parameters included in TF_{PID} when forming $TF_{Test rig}$. Various types of filters were therefore evaluated, including low-pass filters, high-pass filters, and notch filters [49,50]. The first two options were disregarded as they would significantly reduce the controller bandwidth in order to provide adequate attenuation. The most viable option seems the notch filter, which exhibits a unity gain across all frequencies except for its center frequency [51], thereby effectively aiding in the suppression of the resonance. The FB_CTRL_NOTCH_FILTER function block from

the TwinCAT library was utilized for the implementation of the filter. Its TF can be expressed as:

$$TF_{Filt}(s) = \frac{s^2 + \omega_c^2}{s^2 + \delta\omega_c s + \omega_c^2} \quad (11)$$

where δ represents the filter bandwidth and $f_c = \omega_c/2\pi$ is the filter center frequency. The selection of f_c was based on the observed first natural frequency of the mechanical system, as determined in Section 3.1.

To evaluate the filter's performance and determine the appropriate bandwidth, the experiment presented in Section 3.1 was repeated. Specifically, in this case, the notch filter was applied to the LS servomotor command to prevent excitation of the natural frequency (i.e. 5.38 Hz, see Table 3). It must be once again recalled that in this first test the functionality of the implemented filter was assessed without the involvement of the PID controller detailed in Section 4.

Fig. 14. Comparison of purely mechanical response (controller disabled) with and without filter during experiment using sine sweep at $\omega_{MS} = 500$ rpm: (a) Torque recorded over time by the SS torquemeter; (b) Frequency spectrum.

In Fig. 14, the effectiveness of the filter on the LS servomotor command is confirmed. The comparison between the spectrum of the torque measured by the SS torquemeter during the experiments conducted with and without the filter is presented in Fig. 14b. As expected, a significant peak with an amplitude of 30 Nm is observed only when the filter is disabled.

Subsequently, the effects of the filter on the mechatronic system was assessed by enabling also the previously design PID controller. A dedicated experiment is conducted as described in Section 4.3. In Fig. 15, the responses of the mechatronic system, operating at a constant speed of $\omega_{MS} = 1500$ rpm and subject to a torque of -600 Nm, are compared with and without the filter. It is evident that the system with the filter achieves stability. This observation is further supported by the RL plot shown in Fig. 15(b), where the inclusion of TF_{Filter} in $TF_{Test rig}$ leads to an increased critical value of K_p , which steps from 2 to 2.4.

5.2. Influence of controller performance on reducer testing

To test the performance of the proposed control module and prove the importance of its parameter tuning in the context of dynamic reducer testing, a set of experiments were conducted to assess the TE by following the experimental procedure described in [24], i.e. by performing these main steps:

1. Warm-up of the MS reducer to reach the specified oil temperature.
2. Homing procedure to reach a specific initial point from which the TE mapping starts.

Fig. 15. Comparison of response with and without filter in the mechatronic system (controller enabled): (a) experimental test (b) Updated RL to demonstrate the increase of K_p limit implementing the filter.

3. Unload of the SS.
4. Zeroing of the sensors.
5. MS servomotor set at a constant speed.
6. Enable the PID controller to reach the required torque on the SS.
7. Record the encoders feedback to compute the TE.

In this work, the TE experiment was conducted at a constant speed of 1500 rpm for the MS servomotor and with an oil temperature of 25°C in the MS reducer. A torque of -600 Nm was applied to the SS, representing the output shaft of the reducer under test. Three different controller settings were investigated, namely: (i) $K_p = 1.9$ without filter; (ii) $K_p = 2.4$ without filter (exceeding the limit determined through the RL in Fig. 15(b)) and (iii) $K_p = 2.4$ with the filter. Fig. 16 illustrates the results obtained for all cases, with the second case partially plotted due to the anticipated termination of the test. The TE curves clearly demonstrate how the use of incorrect K_p can lead to erroneous TE measurements. They also confirm the importance of incorporating the filter module to prevent damages, especially when high K_p values are demanded to increase the controller dynamic response (curve following). Finally, the conducted experiments indicate that the first parameter set is the most suitable for evaluating the reducer's performance at constant speed, namely where high K_p values are not required, as it delivers more stable torque. The complete experimental dataset can be freely downloaded from the supplementary material section for further elaborations.

Fig. 16. Results of TE experiments at different K_p with and without the notch filter: (a) Torque recorded over time by the SS torquemeter; (b) TE curves over a single SS revolute.

6. Conclusions

The present paper reports on the development of effective strategies for the accurate dynamic characterizations of industrial servomechanisms, as the ones commonly installed in IR. The study is based on a test rig equipped with an active loading system consisting of a second servomechanism and a reducer. After a preliminary description of the experimental equipment aimed at examining the rig functioning and all its physical and logical connections, the research focuses on the rig behavioral modeling by adopting either theoretical and experimental approaches. The proposed analytical formulation has proven effective for predicting the rig's natural frequencies and estimating its mechanical TF. Subsequently, the contributions from the torque PID controller and filter were integrated to form the overall mechatronic TF, which was then utilized to stabilize the rig behavior and enhance its measurement performance. In particular, RL analysis supported the tuning of the closed-loop torque controller. Tests conducted under various operating conditions (speed, torque, and PID parameters) confirmed the validity of the method. Additionally, a filtering approach was employed to further improve the rig's dynamic performance, with the addition of a notch filter enhancing system stability and enabling higher K_p values. Finally, the impact of system stabilization and tuning on the assessment of the servomechanism's transmission performance was examined through well-established transmission error (TE) experiments.

The results of this study, made available to the community through an accessible link, offer valuable insights for advancing servomechanism testing and commissioning experimental apparatus that utilize

active loading systems. These insights lay a foundation for refining control system design and parameter tuning, ultimately enhancing the overall reliability and measurement performance of such systems. Future work will build upon these findings by extending the concepts to curve following, with a specific focus on developing methods and tools for optimizing active load parametrization when enforcing time-varying torque profiles. This research aims to improve the accuracy and efficiency of cam profile tracking, potentially leading to more precise and adaptable control systems across various industrial applications.

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Supplementary material

The experimental data related to this work can be freely downloaded at this Mendeley Data link. <https://doi.org/10.17632/42kxmvfyx.1>

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Alessio Tutarini: Methodology, Software, Investigation, Data curation, Formal analysis. **Pietro Bilancia:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Supervision. **Jhon Freddy Rodríguez León:** Writing, Writing – original draft. **Davide Viappiani:** Software, Methodology. **Marcello Pellicciari:** Funding acquisition, Writing – review and editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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